

Simulation of nutrient management and hydroclimatic effects on coastal water quality and ecological status—The Baltic Himmerfjärden Bay case

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ABSTRACT

Coastal eutrophication is a common problem worldwide, with main drivers including land-based freshwater and nutrient discharges, as well as hydroclimatic and open sea conditions. This study investigates the combined effects of different hydroclimatic and eutrophication management scenarios on coastal water quality and ecological status. As a case study we consider and simulate these scenarios for the Himmerfjärden Bay, situated in the semi-enclosed Baltic Sea. Effects on different eutrophication-relevant variables are assessed for several potential land, coast and/or sea-based management scenarios under different hydroclimatic conditions spanning the range of recent past observations.

Our results show that the land and sea-based management scenarios have different effects on each of the studied eutrophication-relevant coastal variable. In general, management strategies need to target both nitrogen and phosphorus reduction for robust coastal effects. We find hydroclimate as a key non-human eutrophication driver, which can substantially counteract management effects. For hydroclimatic conditions close to the recently experienced average, various management measures can improve water quality and ecosystem status in the studied local Baltic coast. Under projected climate change, however, such improvement will require combined land- and sea-based measures.

1. Introduction

Coastal zones play a crucial societal role and are inhabited by a substantial part of the world population. These zones host a variety of ecosystem services, impacting human life, e.g., in terms of food provision and recreational activities, and ecosystems such as fish nurseries and through nutrient retention (Barbier et al., 2011). Anthropogenic pressures have degraded coastal zones, for example by deteriorating coastal water quality through eutrophication and increased concentration of e.g. heavy metals, microplastics and antibiotics (Kroeze et al., 2016). To solve these problems, various regulatory and international agreement frameworks include or affect coastal zone management, such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD) for European inland and coastal waters, the Marine Framework Directive (MFWD) for European Marine environments, and the HELCOM (Helsinki Commission) Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP) (Borja et al., 2010; HELCOM, 2007).

Eutrophication often occurs due to increased anthropogenic nutrient loading causing higher primary productivity (Nixon, 1995), and is an important coastal problem that can lead to dead zones, loss of biodiversity and toxic algal blooms, damaging coastal ecosystems and their services to society (Smith and Schindler, 2009). Management of coastal eutrophication is challenging as it depends on, links and needs to consider a range of inland, coastal and open sea conditions (Vigouroux et al., 2019), and human activities, such as agriculture, waste water treatment plants, fisheries, and other sectors on land or in the sea (Cloern, 2001).

Hydroclimatic conditions and their changes also affect coastal eutrophication. For example, Bring et al. (2015) show that forthcoming hydroclimatic changes complicate compliance with nutrient remediation targets set by the BSAP. Moreover, the changes influence hydrodynamics (e.g. Chen et al., 2019b), biogeochemical processes, and

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eutrophication, such as in the Baltic Sea (Meier et al., 2012) or the Waituna Lagoon (New Zealand) (Jones et al., 2018). Warmer water temperatures can decrease oxygen concentrations and increase mineralization rates of pelagic and benthic organic matter, thereby increasing phosphorus internal loading and eutrophication (Meier et al., 2012). Therefore, eutrophication management needs to consider the influence of hydroclimate and its changes.

Management measures for reducing eutrophication mostly target reduction of land-based nutrient loads, e.g., by optimizing fertilizer use, restoring and/or constructing wetlands for enhanced nutrient retention, or improving technologies for treating waste water (Ahtiainen et al., 2014). Less commonly employed mitigation measures include food web management or biogeochemical engineering, for example by oxygenating coastal sediments to reduce anoxic internal loading (Conley et al., 2009a). Modelling of the coupled land–coast–marine system that affects coastal eutrophication can facilitate testing of various possible scenarios for its mitigation (Ménesguen et al., 2018; Yuan et al., 2007; Vigouroux et al., 2019). Such scenarios also need to consider how hydroclimate and its variability and change may affect the mitigation results and effectiveness (Ahtiainen et al., 2014).

In this study, we aim to resolve the effectiveness of different types of management measures for achieving policy-required good coastal water quality and ecosystem status, and how different hydroclimatic conditions affect this effectiveness. The investigated types of management measures include land, coast and sea based measures, and the hydroclimatic conditions considered and are selected from a range from recent past conditions. We develop and use a scenario simulation approach to investigate (i) the effects of different possible land, coast and/or sea-based management scenarios for improving coastal water quality and ecological status (European Commission, 2000), and (ii) the influence of hydroclimatic scenarios relevant for projected regional trends towards warmer and wetter conditions, and a comparative divergent scenario, on the effectiveness of the studied management scenarios. As a case study for such investigation, we consider the Himmerfjärden Bay, situated in the Baltic Sea, approximately 50 km south-east of the Swedish capital Stockholm (Fig. 1). This bay represents a relevant example of land–coast–sea interactions receiving discharges of freshwater and nutrients from a major coastal wastewater treatment plant and two rivers, and having a moderate flow exchange with the open sea. For the scenario simulations, we use a relatively simple and scalable modelling approach, recently developed, applied to and validated for the Baltic Sea and another Baltic coastal case by Vigouroux et al. (2019). This study further develops and tests this approach to the different coastal conditions of the Himmerfjärden Bay, considering here also the ecological status implications of the different management scenarios and hydroclimatic conditions according to the requirements for coastal waters of the EU Water Framework Directive (European Commission, 2000).

2. Methods

2.1. Study area

The coastal case of Himmerfjärden Bay (left, Fig. 1) is situated in the south-western part of the Northern Baltic Proper marine basin of the Baltic Sea (right, Fig. 1). The two main freshwater discharges to the Himmerfjärden Bay are from the Södertälje canal, flowing into Igelstaviken (average discharge of $6.1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the period 2000–2009, data from the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)) and the Trosa river flowing into Trosafjärden (average discharge of $4.1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the period 2000–2009, data from SMHI). These discharges account for 68% of the total freshwater flow into the bay. Smaller streams, spread throughout the land catchment of the bay account for the remaining 32% of the freshwater discharge. The catchment area is $1,286 \text{ km}^2$, with around 20% of agricultural land and a population of 17,000 inhabitants (Schiewer, 2008). Land-based

waterborne nutrient contributions by runoff account for more than 50% of the total nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) loading into the bay from point, riverine and atmospheric sources (Fig. 2). Point source loads directly into the coastal waters account for around 40% of the total nutrient loading to the bay, of which the major part originates from the Himmerfjärdsverken wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). This serves around 300,000 inhabitants of the southern Stockholm region and releases into the specific coastal Himmerfjärden coastal basin (CB) outlined in Fig. 1 (left) (Franzén et al., 2011).

The Himmerfjärden Bay is thermally stratified in the summer, which creates frequent seasonal hypoxia in its inner part and occasional events in the outer CBs (Bonaglia et al., 2014). Sea ice cover forms mostly in the northern CBs and impedes wind mixing only during severe winters (Engqvist and Stenström, 2009). The bay is connected to the open sea through a sound situated in the south, linking the Asköfjärden and Svärdsfjärden CBs (directly eastward of Asköfjärden) with the Northern Baltic Proper marine basin (Fig. 1, right). Shallow channels also connect the bay to the open sea in the south-west and to the Stockholm archipelago in the south-east. The bay is characterized by a relatively long retention time, typically above 50 days (Engqvist, 1996).

As for most coastal areas of the Baltic Sea, openly available data is limited also in the Himmerfjärden Bay. Within the simulation period (2000–2009) 6 monitoring stations provide physical measurement data (salinity and temperature), and 4 monitoring stations provide biogeochemical measurements, for the years 2008 and 2009. These measurements have been made at the surface and bottom, twice a year, during the summer months of July and August. These measurements are used for model validation, while more temporally detailed information, obtained from monthly measurements during one year (2015) is used for calibration of site specific rates in the model. More detailed site specific data exist but are overall relatively limited around the Baltic Sea coast, and may not be openly accessible. The relatively limited open data accessibility, together with the physical characteristics and different types of land-based nutrient loadings to the coast, make the Himmerfjärden Bay an interesting representative case for our coastal investigation scope.

2.2. Hydroclimatic conditions

To investigate various hydroclimatic conditions in the Himmerfjärden Bay case, we use available data over the period 2000–2009 to classify river discharges to the sea (R , $\text{m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and net heat flux over the coastal–marine area (H , W m^{-2}). The latter quantifies the net solar energy received by the sea (energy gain through net downward shortwave radiation minus energy losses through net upward longwave radiation, latent heat flux, and sensible heat flux). R and H have been identified to be main hydrodynamic drivers for salinity and water temperature, as well as important drivers for biogeochemical processes due to their influence on water temperature and nutrient supply (Chen et al., 2019b; Meier et al., 2012). Our classification of some representative data-given hydroclimatic conditions is based on the relative difference of specific year conditions from the 2000–2009 period-average R and H conditions in the Himmerfjärden Bay and the Baltic Sea, affecting the coastal sea-boundary conditions (Table 1). The condition–year 2005 is classified as dry and cold ($R_- H_-$, dry–cold), the condition–year 2003 as particularly dry and warm ($R_- H_+$, dry–warm), and the condition–year 2000 as particularly wet and particularly warm ($R_+ H_+$, wet–warm). These condition–years are selected as comparative scenarios of projected change trends towards warmer and wetter conditions (The BACC II Author Team, 2015) and the divergent dry–cold conditions that are most representative of the recent average local/regional hydroclimate (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Left: Delimitation of different coastal basins (CBs) in the Himmerfjärden Bay; Right: The Himmerfjärden Bay location in the Baltic Sea and its marine basin Northern Baltic Proper (NBP) that forms the coastal boundary to the open sea. The right panel also outlines the other main marine basins (with associated acronyms) of the Baltic Sea.

Fig. 2. Loads of total nitrogen (TN, first column) and total phosphorus (TP, second column) for the investigated hydroclimatic condition-years (dry-cold: $R_{-}H_{-}$, dry-warm: $R_{-}H_{+}$, and wet-warm: $R_{++}H_{++}$) compared with the 2000–2009 period-average conditions for the Himmerfjärden Bay (top row) and the Baltic Sea (bottom row).

2.3. Management scenarios

For each hydroclimatic condition-year, nine management scenarios are investigated corresponding to different possible eutrophication mitigation measures. All scenarios are run for 30 years by repeating forcing data for each considered condition-year until steady state simulation results are reached. Consideration of steady state conditions removes short-term transient effects and the results represent the direction of evolution of the system under the studied management scenarios and hydroclimatic conditions. The nine management scenarios comprise a base case scenario (S_0), three land mitigation scenarios ($S_{P,S}$, S_R , and $S_{P,S+R}$, with two sub-scenarios $S_{(P,S+R)_N}$, and $S_{(P,S+R)_P}$), a coastal mitigation scenario where coastal water conditions are assumed aerobic

(S_{Aer}), a sea mitigation scenario (S_{Sea}), and a combined sea and land mitigation scenario ($S_{P,S+R+Sea}$), as further listed and outlined below:

- S_0 : Base case scenario of current management conditions, with repeated representative hydroclimatic conditions for each condition-year.
- $S_{P,S}$: 50% reduction in total nitrogen (TN) and total phosphorus (TP) loads from all the point sources (mostly from the WWTP situated in the Himmerfjärden CB), as might be achieved by enhanced water treatment technologies used in the specific WWTP releasing into this coast.

Table 1

Hydroclimatic condition–year classification based on hydrodynamic forcing conditions for the Himmerfjärden Bay and the Baltic Sea, using data for river discharges (R) and net heat flux (H). The condition–year 2005 is classified as dry–cold ($R_H_$); the condition–year 2003 is classified as dry–warm (R_H_+); the condition–year 2000 is classified as wet–warm ($R_{++}H_{++}$). River discharge data are obtained from the Swedish Meteorological Institute (SMHI) for the Himmerfjärden Bay and the Helsinki Commission (HELCOM) for the whole Baltic Sea, and averaged for the corresponding condition–year/period. Net heat flux is obtained from the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) for both the Himmerfjärden Bay and the Baltic Sea (excluding the westernmost part, Fig. 1), and averaged for the corresponding condition–year/period.

Year/Period	Himmerfjärden Bay				Baltic Sea			
	$R_H_$ 2005	R_H_+ 2003	$R_{++}H_{++}$ 2000	Period average 2000–2009	$R_H_$ 2005	R_H_+ 2003	$R_{++}H_{++}$ 2000	Period average 2000–2009
River discharge ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)	11.6	9.8	20.1	14.5	13876	10752	16325	13683
(% relative difference from period average)	(–20)	(–32)	(39)		(1.4)	(–21)	(19)	
Net heat flux (W m^{-2})	3.1	6.0	17.6	2.33	–4.2	8.2	16.3	3.07
(% relative difference from period average)	(33)	(158)	(655)		(–237)	(167)	(431)	
Catchment Air temperature (CRU) ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	6.16	5.82	6.90	6.26	5.4	5.08	6.12	5.47
River discharge; main simulated rivers ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)	11.6	9.8	20.1	14.5	9842	6159	10162	8617
Net heat flux; model grid (W m^{-2})	4.9	6.2	19.1	3.3	–4.84	7.37	16.66	2.58

- S_R : Same absolute load reduction as for S_{PS} , distributed over the riverine loads (proportionally to their current load contributions), as might be achieved by more and/or more effective catchment measures for nutrient input mitigation (e.g., through improved agricultural nutrient management), downstream load capturing (e.g., in constructed buffer zones and wetlands), and/or enhanced water treatment technologies used in all WWTPs across all hydrological catchments of this coastline.
- S_{PS+R} : Combination of S_{PS} and S_R with reduction of both TN and TP. Sub-scenarios $S_{(PS+R)_N}$ and $S_{(PS+R)_P}$ correspond to S_{PS+R} with only TN reduction and only TP reduction, respectively.
- S_{Aer} : Water conditions assumed aerobic in the whole Himmerfjärden Bay resulting in no internal loading of phosphorus, as might be achieved, e.g., by local coastal measures of artificial oxygenation or chemical binding of phosphorus (Conley et al., 2009a).
- S_{Sea} : Good ecological status (GES, as defined by HELCOM) reached in the sea and determining the coastal boundary conditions of the Northern Baltic Proper (NBP) marine basin (Fig. 1, right), as might be achieved by measures and improvements in the other land and coastal areas of the NBP and the whole Baltic Sea, with potential contributions also by artificial sea oxygenation (Conley et al., 2009a).
- $S_{PS+R+Sea}$: Combination of S_{PS+R} and S_{Sea} .

Consideration and simulation of these scenarios facilitates our targeted investigation of the coastal water quality and ecological status effects of various potential management strategies for coastal eutrophication mitigation. Scenario S_{PS} corresponds to technological improvements for nutrient removal in the Himmerfjärdsverken WWTP. Scenario S_R corresponds to multiple possible catchment measures. These include agricultural, industrial, urban/household, as well as legacy source (Destouni and Jarsjö, 2018) management of nutrient inputs/releases in the coastal catchments. They also include downstream nutrient capture measures, e.g., in constructed buffers and wetlands, as well as technological nutrient-removal improvements in other WWTPs across the catchments. Scenario S_{Aer} corresponds to improved oxygen conditions in the whole Himmerfjärden Bay allowing for investigation of possible locally applied geoengineering measures for increasing the coastal water oxygenation and/or chemically immobilize phosphorus in the sediments of this bay. It also allows for investigation of the role of internal phosphorus loading for the managed eutrophication evolution of the Himmerfjärden Bay. Scenario S_{Sea} corresponds to good ecological status being achieved in the NBP marine basin at the boundary of the Himmerfjärden Bay, through various combinations or all of the above-mentioned land and coast-based management measures being applied in other parts of the NBP and of the Baltic Sea affecting the NBP. This is not trivial to attain as internal loading of phosphorus may maintain and reinforce eutrophication conditions in the sea (Stigebrandt, 2018) and, e.g., land-based measures may be ineffective in

reducing nutrient loads to the sea (Destouni et al., 2017; Destouni and Jarsjö, 2018), while sea-based geoengineering measures may also be ineffective in reducing hypoxia and eutrophication in the Baltic Sea itself (Conley et al., 2009a).

2.4. Modelling approach and application

Our modelling approach is based on the methodology developed in Vigouroux et al. (2019) and schematized in their Figure 7. In this study, two scales are considered: the coastal zone scale (Himmerfjärden Bay) and the open sea scale (Baltic Sea). Water quality conditions for these two scales are simulated using the same scalable modelling approach. Water quality simulations necessitate hydrodynamic results, which are obtained using a relatively fine hydrodynamic model on the coastal zone scale and a coarser model resolution on the Baltic Sea scale. These hydrodynamic simulations are aggregated on the CBs for the coastal scale (Fig. 1, left) and on the coarser main marine basins for the Baltic Sea scale (Fig. 1, right) and used to drive the water quality model for these CB/marine basin aggregations.

The use of the same modelling approach on both scales ensures consistency in the representation of the coastal–marine boundary conditions of water quality, using the present Baltic Sea-scale model results, rather than output data from some other Baltic Sea model, to represent and quantify these conditions. Moreover, due to the relatively limited observation data accessibility on the coastal scale, a rigorous calibration and validation of the Himmerfjärden Bay model has not been possible, which implies relatively high modelling uncertainty on that scale. On the Baltic Sea scale, however, data availability is sufficient, and the water quality model has been fully calibrated and validated on that scale (Vigouroux et al., 2019). Using a similar modelling approach on both the coastal and the Baltic Sea scale allows for model-data discrepancy assessment (e.g., of the model representation of permanently anoxic conditions) on the Baltic Sea scale (Vigouroux et al., 2019), which can also to some degree improve model use and confidence on the coastal scale. Specific coastal-system calibration is of course still needed for accurate model predictions, but this study aims at scenario analysis of effect implications of various management measure and hydroclimatic condition combinations for coastal water quality and ecosystem status, rather than at specific predictions of the latter. As such, some reduction of coastal modelling uncertainties is achieved by simulating results at long-term steady state conditions, and thereby removing transient effects and associated uncertainties. Scenario result comparisons are then relatively robust in indicating directions of change rather than predicting specific coastal conditions at different points in time. Calibration of the Baltic Sea model (period 2001–2002; 2009), and its validation (period 2003–2008) and the calibration of the Himmerfjärden Bay model are described in Supplementary Materials (SM) Section S2.2; validation of the coastal model (period 2008–2009) is described in SM Section S2.3. The Baltic Sea water quality model results are just used as boundary conditions to

drive the Himmerfjärden Bay water quality model, and are not further analysed in this work.

The three-dimensional FVCOM model (Finite Volume Community Ocean Model) has been used (Chen et al., 2003) for independently simulating both the Baltic Sea and Himmerfjärden Bay hydrodynamic conditions. The FVCOM model simulates water motion using the primitive equations of momentum, which are discretized by the finite volume method, ensuring a good mass conservation. The space domain is discretized horizontally with an unstructured triangular grid and vertically with uniform sigma layers, allowing improved representation of water bodies with complex coastlines and bathymetry compared to structured rectangular grid. FVCOM has been successfully implemented for a wide range of coastal zones and oceans (e.g., Chen et al. 2011, 2016, Chen et al. 2019a).

Hydrodynamics results of salinity and temperature are aggregated on CBs (Fig. 1, left) or Baltic marine basins (Fig. 1, right), depending on the model scale, representing areas with relatively homogeneous conditions. These CBs/marine basins are divided into two vertical layers separated at the pycnocline, which is the zone of least vertical mixing. Velocity results are used to calculate the flow among the CBs/marine basins and between the vertical layers. The water quality model is then applied on each layer of each CB/marine basin. Detailed setup of the hydrodynamic model is described SM Section S2.1 and its calibration is described SM Section S5.

Water quality conditions of the Himmerfjärden Bay and the Baltic Sea are simulated based on a simple carbon-based biogeochemical model developed by Kiirikki et al. (2001, 2006), as described, applied and validated for the coastal Archipelago Sea and the whole Baltic Sea in Vigouroux et al. (2019). The ecosystem part of the model, which is based on the oceanic phytoplankton model developed by Tyrrell (1999), represents the other phytoplankton, the cyanobacteria, and the concentrations of organic nutrients (nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and carbon (C) in detritus) and dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN: ammonium, nitrite and nitrate) and phosphorus (DIP: phosphate) (Kiirikki et al., 2001). The sediment part accounts for the nutrients (N, P and C) in mobilizable (volatile) sediments and the iron-bound P. It represents rates of detritus sedimentation, sediment mineralization and denitrification, and release of iron-bound P (internal loading). The latter is modelled as depending on the CO_2 efflux from the sediments (Kiirikki et al., 2006). This efflux is used as a proxy of microbial reduction pathways and oxygen consumption at the sediment–water interface (Kiirikki et al., 2006; Lehtoranta et al., 2009). The present model has been modified from Vigouroux et al. (2019) to improve the representation of anoxic processes by calculating the anoxic area of sediments in each CB/marine basin; this is represented as a linear function of the CO_2 efflux and the internal loading of P is limited to the anoxic area. The complete set of equations and rates are presented in SM Section S3. Further details and discussion of the carbon-based model are provided in Vigouroux et al. (2019).

Chl a (Chlorophyll a) is calculated from the modelled algal biomass (CA ($mg L^{-1}$)) using the following equation:

$$Chl a \text{ (}\mu g L^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{CA \times C_{inA} \times 1000}{R_{C-Chl a}} \quad (1)$$

Where $C_{inA}(-)$ is the mass ratio of carbon to algae ($C : CA$) defined as 0.11 and $R_{C-Chl a}(-)$ is the mass ratio of carbon to Chl a ($C : Chl a$), defined to 30 during the spring prosperous period and 60 during more competitive periods such as the summer (Wasmund and Siegel, 2008). This equation does not allow a precise calculation of the Chl a concentration dependence on species and environment (e.g. Wasmund and Siegel (2008)), but gives a rough estimate suitable for comparisons, as also used in the BALTSEM model (Savchuk et al., 2012).

2.5. Scenario setup

Simulations of scenario S_0 for the three condition–years have been carried out by repeating the forcing data to obtain 30 iteration–years. Hydroclimatic forcing (1 year time series from the first to the last day of the considered year) for water quality has been repeated 30 times for each condition–year, and hydrodynamic forcing, obtained by 15 repetition of the hydroclimatic and boundary condition forcing (1 year time series), has been repeated twice for each condition–year. This allows the system to reach an equilibrium quasi steady state (with small inter-annual variations between iteration–years, and stable sediment pools). Initial conditions are set at the first day of the year, by restarting the simulation after a 15 iteration–year run of the calibrated model. Boundary conditions are set by the water quality simulation results of the second iteration–year on the Northern Baltic Proper for each condition–year.

The other scenarios simulations (except S_0) are initialized at the first day of the year, using the last simulation step of the corresponding condition–year S_0 simulation. Thus, these simulations start at the same equilibrium conditions as obtained for the base case scenario for each condition–year considered. The scenarios S_{PS} , S_R , S_{PS+R} , S_{PS+R_N} , and S_{PS+R_P} represent land-based management measures; for S_{PS} , point source nutrient loadings are reduced by 50%; for S_R , an equivalent absolute reduction is distributed over the riverine loads proportionally to their current load contributions; for S_{PS+R} , point source and riverine loading are reduced similarly to S_{PS} and S_R ; for S_{PS+R_N} and S_{PS+R_P} nitrogen and phosphorus are reduced similarly to S_{PS+R} , respectively. All other forcings are kept unchanged. In the nutrient loading data from SMHI, point source loads are constant over the years, therefore nutrient load reductions for these scenarios are independent from the hydroclimatic forcing. For S_{Aer} , all forcings are kept similar to S_0 and the model equations are modified to remove anoxic effects (no internal loading) in the whole Himmerfjärden Bay. For S_{Sea} , the simulated concentration of each pelagic variables in the NBP is divided by a constant (depending on the condition–year) to ensure that good ecological status targets are met for DIN, DIP, Chl a, and for TN and TP, as defined for the NBP basin by the HELCOM BSAP (given in Section 2.6.2). Total nutrients are taken as the addition of nutrients in the algal pool, the inorganic pool and the detritus pool and are likely to be underestimated as only bioavailable nutrient inputs are considered by the model. The good ecological status in the NBP leads to a reduction of the DIN, DIP and Chl a concentrations in the inflowing water to the coast from this boundary basin of 22%, 61%, and 80%, respectively, for the $R_{++}H_{++}$ condition–year, 0%, 58%, and 78%, respectively, for the $R_{--}H_{+}$ condition–year, and 0%, 49%, and 69%, respectively, for the $R_{-}H_{-}$ condition–year. The S_{Sea} scenario thus yields significant reduction of DIP and Chl a flowing from the open sea to the bay and relatively small to no reduction of the DIN inflow. For the $S_{PS+R+Sea}$ scenario, the land-based (N and P) and sea-based (N, P, and Chl a) loads are reduced similarly to S_{PS+R} and S_{Sea} , respectively.

2.6. Ecological status

Calculations of Ecological Quality Ratio (EQR) and Ecological Status (ES) are made according to the 2018 version of the regulations by the Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management (HVMFS) for classification and environmental norms of surface waters. The calculation of EQR depends on the type of CB, defined by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency in Naturvårdsverket (2006), and the CBs considered here consist of three types, numbered in the regulations as 24 for the Igelstaviken and Hällsfjärden, 14 for the boundary coastal/marine basin and 12n for the remaining CBs. For these types, summer comprises the months of July and August and winter the months of December, January and February according to the applicable regulations.

Fig. 3. Steady-state component status classification for the base case scenario S_0 (first column, Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (DIN); second column, Dissolved Inorganic Phosphorus (DIP); third column: Chlorophyll a (Chl a) for R_-H_- condition-year (2005) (first row), R_-H_+ condition-year (2003) (second row) and $R_{++}H_{++}$ condition-year (2000) (third row).

2.6.1. Nutrients and Chlorophyll a

The EQR calculations are made for the DIN, DIP and Chl a variables, as they are the main calibrated variables of the model, and constitute important eutrophication indicators, with winter DIN and DIP concentrations being related to spring algae blooms, and summer Chl a concentrations indicating summer productivity and possible harmful algae blooms. Calculations of EQRs for DIN, DIP and Chl a have been made considering the last 5 simulation years for each CB under each management scenario and hydroclimatic condition-year combination. For DIN and DIP, only winter concentrations are considered, and for Chl a, the summer concentrations are considered. The EQRs are calculated using monthly averages of the simulated concentrations,

as representative of regulation requirements. For each of the water quality/eutrophication components DIN, DIP and Chl a, the associated EQR ad ES are further calculated as follows:

- The surface layer of the modelled results is used. This approximates the HVMFS regulation requirements stating that DIN and DIP measurements should be done in the surface layer, up to the minimum between the pycnocline and 10 m depth, and for Chl a, the measurements should be done at 0.5 m.
- The EQR is defined as the ratio of the reference value to the observation value:

Fig. 4. Proportion of coastal basin (CB) area reaching Good Component Status under the baseline Scenario S_0 . Whiskers represent the status classification uncertainty based on $\pm 10\%$ status variation around the average Ecological Status classification.

For DIN and DIP, the reference value depends on the CB type and the monthly average of simulated salinity.

For Chl a, the reference value depends on the CB type, the monthly average of simulated salinity, and the reference value for total nitrogen concentrations. The definition of the reference values also depends on the sea measured salinity, which is taken from the model simulations as the monthly average of the simulated salinity at the boundary coastal/marine basin.

- The calculated daily EQR is further averaged over the 5 last years of the simulation.
- The status classification is made according to the EQR limit defined in the HVMFS regulation (Havs- och vattenmyndigheten, 2018)
- The ES of each assessed water quality/eutrophication component is obtained by normalizing the EQR (according to Formula 2.1 in Attachment 5 of the HVMFS regulation (Havs- och vattenmyndigheten, 2018))

2.6.2. Ecological status compliance

The ES classification for each considered component in each CB is derived as: $ES < 0.2$ is classified as poor, $0.2 \leq ES < 0.4$ is classified as insufficient, $0.4 \leq ES < 0.6$ is classified as moderate, $0.6 \leq ES < 0.8$ is classified as good, and $0.8 \leq ES \leq 1$ is classified as high. The proportion of CB reaching Good Component Status (GCS) is then calculated by considering the ratio of the area of CBs classified as having good or high ES by the total area of the Himmerfjärden Bay (excluding the boundary coastal/marine basin). Uncertainty in the classification is assessed by considering a possible concentration variation leading

to an ES variation of $\pm 10\%$ around each respective average value, which corresponds to around half of an ES class. This uncertainty analysis does not explicitly represent underlying (model, data, ES class) uncertainties, but allows for assessment and visualization of sensitivity in ES classification results to such uncertainty combinations.

For the boundary coastal/marine basin, the classifications of winter DIN and DIP and summer Chl a concentrations are made according to the marine HELCOM BSAP targets for the NBP. If the DIN, DIP and Chl a concentrations are lower than $40.6 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, $7.75 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $1.65 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively, the component ES is here classified as “Achieve” and classified as “Fail” otherwise.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Base case scenario

Steady state results under the base case scenarios (S_0) are compared between the hydroclimatic condition-years in Figs. 3 and 4. Under wet-warm conditions ($R_{++}H_{++}$, 2000) the classification is robust for both DIN and DIP, with few CBs reaching good component status, while the Chl a status exhibits a north-south gradient from high to insufficient. Most of the CBs have moderate status for DIN, DIP and Chl a, with Chl a closer to the good than to the insufficient status. Under dry-warm conditions ($R_{-}H_{+}$, 2003), the classification is also robust for DIN and DIP, with most of the CBs having moderate status and the DIN status being comparable to $R_{++}H_{++}$. For Chl a, most of the CBs have moderate or worse status, but more than half of the bay is close to good status. Under dry-cold conditions ($R_{-}H_{-}$, 2005), DIP and Chl a are generally better. Most of the CBs have a status close to good component status or higher for DIP and Chl a, and moderate status for DIN, comparable to $R_{-}H_{+}$ and $R_{++}H_{++}$.

The lack of validation data and the comparison with available monitoring data indicate that specific status classifications under steady state conditions are subject to uncertainties. The error bars indicate possible shifts in resulting status classification between good and moderate for the DIN, DIP and Chl a. For Chl a, comparison between model results and validation data for summer concentrations (Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) calculated in SM Section S2.3 indicates that the model likely underestimates summer concentrations and could lead to the model-based status classification reaching good status for some CBs that may actually be classified as moderate. For DIN and DIP, the model-based status classification and error bars are calculated based on winter concentrations, and thus do not directly correspond to the comparison between model results and validation data (SM Section S2.3), which is based on summer DIN and DIP concentrations. Nevertheless, the error bars in Fig. 4 (and following result figures) still indicate possible status classification uncertainties implied by concentration variations around a corresponding seasonal average concentration.

The worse DIP status under wet-warm conditions compared with dry-warm conditions can be explained by the larger runoff and thereby larger nutrient loading in the wet-warm condition-year. The larger runoff, however, cannot explain the better Chl a status under wet-warm than dry-warm conditions, and the comparable DIN status for these conditions. This is rather explained by summer Chl a concentrations depending less on winter nutrient concentrations than the spring bloom (Vahtera et al., 2007). Therefore, better Chl a status under wet-warm conditions may be due to lower summer water temperature compared with dry-warm conditions (SM Figure S14). The higher average heat flux for the wet-warm condition-year leads to warmer winter temperature, while summer water temperatures are lower than under dry-warm conditions. This better summer Chl a status, due to lower cyanobacteria concentration under wet-warm conditions, also leads to less nitrogen fixation (Vahtera et al., 2007), which compensates higher nutrient loading and can explain the comparable DIN status between wet-warm and dry-warm conditions, and the spatial differences between these two condition-years. On the Himmerfjärden Bay

Fig. 5. Proportion of coastal basin (CB) area reaching Good Component Status for DIN (A), DIP (B), and Chl a (C) under main investigated scenarios (S_0 , S_{PS} , S_R , S_{PS+R} , S_{Aer} , S_{Sea} , $S_{PS+R+Sea}$). Whiskers represent the status classification uncertainty based on $\pm 10\%$ status variation around the average Ecological Status classification. The explicit spatial results underlying the results summary illustrated here are provided in SM, Figures S1 to S9.

Fig. 6. Proportion of coastal basin (CB) area reaching Good Component Status for DIN (A), DIP (B), and Chl a (C) under the scenario S_{PS+R} and the sub-scenarios $S_{(PS+R)_N}$ and $S_{(PS+R)_P}$. Whiskers represent the status classification uncertainty based on $\pm 10\%$ status variation around the average Ecological Status classification.

scale, dry-warm and dry-cold condition-years have relatively close runoff and nutrient loading values, while heat flux is lower for the dry-cold condition-year, which explains the generally better status for the DIP and Chl a components under dry-cold conditions. The comparable DIN status between dry-warm and dry-cold condition-years can be explained by an accumulation of DIN in the coastal system in the latter condition-year. This is due to lower DIP concentrations and releases from the sediments (no internal loading under the dry-cold condition-year) limiting primary production and denitrification under those conditions.

3.2. Enhanced management scenarios

Steady state results for the various enhanced management scenarios in different hydroclimatic condition-years are compared in Fig. 5. Overall, the land-based scenarios that remove an equal proportion of nitrogen and phosphorus loading are the most effective for improving DIN status. The sea-based scenario S_{Sea} is less effective for DIN as it removes more phosphorus than nitrogen. Moreover, the loading from the open Baltic Sea to the bay, relative to the loading from land, is greater for phosphorus than for nitrogen (Engqvist, 1996), which explains the lower effectiveness of the land-based management scenarios for improving the DIP compared to the DIN status. Under dry-cold conditions, the combined land-based scenario S_{PS+R} leads to more than 50% of the bay reaching GCS for DIP and 80% for DIN, similarly to the

effects of the combined land-sea scenario. However, the effectiveness of the land-based S_{PS+R} scenario decreases greatly for the DIN and DIP components under warmer and wetter hydroclimatic conditions. For Chl a, however, the S_{PS+R} scenario leads to GCS being reached over more than 50% of the bay across all hydroclimatic conditions. Under the S_{PS+R} scenario, Chl a status improvements are higher than DIN or DIP status improvements under warmer conditions and lower under dry-cold conditions, further exemplifying the complex and non-linear relationship between Chl a and nutrients (Ménésguen et al., 2018). In general, note that ES result reliability also depends on underlying uncertainties, as indicated by the $\pm 10\%$ status class error bars in Fig. 5; for example, model parametrization is uncertain under the lack of coastal data for model calibration in the Himmerfjärden Bay.

Fig. 6 shows the effects on DIN (panel A), DIP (panel B) and Chl a (panel C) status of land-based (point and riverine) load reductions for both nitrogen and phosphorus, and for only nitrogen and only phosphorus. Across all hydroclimatic conditions, reducing only nitrogen or only phosphorus performs generally worse than reducing both across all water quality components. For dry-cold conditions, removing only nitrogen results in a worsening of DIP status compared to the base scenario (Fig. 5B), which can be explained by a stronger nitrogen limitation in some CBs leading to higher winter DIP concentrations. For the DIN status, removing only nitrogen results in a slight improvement of DIN status compared to removing both nutrients under dry-cold conditions. This can be explained by an accumulation of DIN in the

coastal system if too much phosphorus is removed, which is further supported by the worsening of DIN status under the dry–warm conditions (Fig. 5A) for the combined land–sea $S_{P_{S+R+Sea}}$ compared with the combined land-based $S_{P_{S+R}}$ scenario. Indeed, in the $S_{P_{S+R+Sea}}$ scenario, the open sea DIN conditions are unchanged, and only phosphorus and algae biomass are reduced.

Negative effects following major phosphorus reductions have also been observed, e.g., in the Neuse River estuary (USA) and by the Rhine River, becoming phosphorus-limited and yielding a larger export of nitrogen that accentuated eutrophication in the load-receiving/affected Wadden Sea and Norwegian coast (Conley et al., 2009b).

Overall, our results show that reducing the loads from land of both nutrients mostly yields the highest improvements of coastal water quality in the case study of Himmerfjärden Bay. However, the proportions of nitrogen and phosphorus load removal could be optimized, as removing only nitrogen performs better than removing both nutrients for DIN status but can lead to a worsening of DIP status under dry–cold conditions. The land-based scenarios simulated here lead to relatively more DIN than DIP being removed in total from the coastal system, due to the proportion of loading from the open sea relative to that from land being greater for phosphorus than for nitrogen (Engqvist, 1996). Thereby, removing the same relative share of nitrogen and phosphorus loading from land lowers the DIN/DIP ratio in the coastal system, which can increase cyanobacteria blooms (Chen et al., 2013) and partly explain the slightly greater effect on Chl a of reducing only phosphorus compared to reducing both nutrients from land under dry–cold conditions (Fig. 6C). While cyanobacteria growth is also affected by light availability, wind mixing and water temperature (Kanoshina et al., 2003), optimization of dual nutrient management strategies to control the resulting coastal DIN/DIP ratio would allow eutrophication reduction without increasing cyanobacteria blooms (Chen et al., 2013). Such further optimization simulations rely on a precise description of the nutrient balance and dynamics in the system, requiring a thorough calibration and validation of the model. Therefore, they are outside of the scope of the present study and call for further, follow-up research.

The coastal management scenario S_{Aer} does not improve compliance with GCS for the DIN and DIP component (Fig. 5A). For the DIP component (Fig. 5B), it results in a very slight increased GCS compliance only under dry–warm conditions. For the Chl a component (Fig. 5C), S_{Aer} improve compliance with GCS similarly to the combined land-based scenario $S_{P_{S+R}}$ under dry–warm conditions with no effects under dry–cold and little effects under wet–warm conditions. The improvements in Chl a status may be overestimated, and the effects on DIP status underestimated, due to too high vertical mixing in the hydrodynamic model resulting in earlier onset of anoxic conditions. Part of the resulting deep DIP may then be available for algal uptake instead of being stored in the deeper layer. While internal loading enhances Baltic Sea eutrophication (Stigebrandt, 2018), our coastal results indicate that seasonal anoxia, and associated internal loading of phosphorus, is not the main driver of eutrophication in the studied coastal zone. Moreover, the implementation of the coastal S_{Aer} management scenario, through artificial oxygenation or chemical binding of phosphorus, presents risks, such as creation of a large pool of easily mobilizable phosphorus or toxicity of the chemical precipitate (Conley et al., 2009a), and could increase nitrogen export to the Baltic Sea, as indicated by the slight decrease of DIN status for this scenario compared to the base scenario under the dry–warm conditions (Fig. 5A).

The sea-based scenario S_{Sea} has limited effect on the DIN component, as open sea boundary conditions for this component are already close to GES. However, for both DIP and Chl a components, the S_{Sea} scenario has the overall greatest improvement effects (after and dominating the effects of the combined scenario $S_{P_{S+R+Sea}}$). The effects of open sea may be somewhat overestimated, as indicated by slightly too high modelled summer concentrations of DIP in the southernmost CB. However, the results are consistent with a high proportion of total phosphorus entering this coast from the open sea, as reported

by Engqvist (1996), and with reports of important open sea conditions for coastal eutrophication also in other coastal areas (Jones et al., 2018). Improved open sea water quality conditions can lead to water quality improvements over substantial coastal areas (e.g. SM Figures S8 and S9 (third row, second column), and Vigouroux et al. (2019) Figure 5). However, these effects may be less strong where land-based influence is stronger, due to the flow direction and the buffer role of archipelagos and coastal zones (Bonsdorff et al., 1997). For the Himmerfjärden Bay, which is valued for water related recreational activities and recreational housing (Franzén et al., 2011), some parts with higher social values due to their proximity with cities and accessibility, such as Igelstaviken, might benefit less from improved open sea conditions.

The combined land- and sea-based scenario $S_{P_{S+R+Sea}}$ generally leads to the greatest overall coastal status improvements. For the DIN component, its effects are dominated by those of the combined land-based scenario $S_{P_{S+R}}$, the latter being improved under wet–warm conditions and worsened under dry–warm conditions. For DIP and Chl a, its effects are dominated by the sea-based scenario S_{Sea} .

3.3. Role of hydroclimate for management effectiveness

Fig. 5 shows that management scenarios are generally the most effective under dry–cold conditions and the least effective under warmer conditions. Under wet–warm conditions, only management scenarios that include sea-based measures (S_{Sea} and $S_{P_{S+R+Sea}}$) lead to substantial coastal improvements for DIN and DIP.

The dry–warm condition–year may be representative of a possible trend towards warmer and drier summers (The BACC II Author Team, 2015). Under such conditions, comprehensive land-based management measures can still yield substantial coastal improvements for the winter DIN and summer Chl a components (with more than 70% of the coastal area being close to GCS for these components), while the winter DIP concentrations remain high. The wet–warm condition–year may be representative of the overall regional wetter–warmer trends projected by climate models (The BACC II Author Team, 2015). Under such conditions, land-based management measures only result in marginal coastal improvements for the DIN and DIP components, while they result in substantial improvements for the Chl a component. Sea-based measures can lead to substantial coastal improvements, with more than 80% of the coastal area being close to or achieving GCS for DIP and Chl a. The combined land- and sea-based scenario $S_{P_{S+R+Sea}}$ yields the greatest coastal improvements, with more than additive effects for the DIN component compared to the separate $S_{P_{S+R}}$ and S_{Sea} scenarios.

Overall, our results indicate that in this semi-enclosed bay, coastal eutrophication management may presumably be further complicated by the forthcoming warmer and wetter climate conditions (moving towards more $R_{++}H_{++}$ years) projected by climate models. Such hydroclimatic trends have also been found for other coastal areas of the world, such as the Waituna Lagoon (New Zealand) (Jones et al., 2018), and for the Baltic Sea as a whole (Meier et al., 2012). For the Himmerfjärden Bay, improving open sea conditions is then the most effective strategy for reaching good coastal status for DIP and Chl a components, and also for the DIN component when combined with reduction of land-based nutrient loading.

3.4. Model limitations and uncertainties

Several simplifications have been made in the model representation of the complex coastal system and its land–sea and climate interactions. Sea ice is not represented in the model, leading to uncertainties in the model representation of energy balance and overestimation of wind mixing. However, sea ice impeding wind mixing only occurs in severe winters (Engqvist and Stenström, 2009) and these effects are most pronounced in the winter period, when biogeochemical rates are relatively low. The applicability of this simplification is supported by the salinity results, which are within the observation range, indicating

a reasonable description of the horizontal water transport. Considering heat flux as a forcing neglects the heat flux-atmosphere feedback, which can lead to inaccurate temperature but this is not seen in the present simulations (Figure SM S14). The modelled stratification of salinity and temperature, however, is weaker than observed, indicating too high vertical mixing. This could be caused by a relatively coarse mesh, that cannot fully capture the fine variations of the bathymetry.

The water quality model validation for the Himmerfjärden Bay, with slightly too high DIP concentration in the Asköfjärden CB, suggests that the influence of the open sea may be somewhat overestimated, which could in turn underestimate the effects of land-based management scenarios. Such overestimation can be corrected by adding further model CBs between the open sea and the boundary conditions at the coast, or through more computationally intensive hydrodynamic simulations. Limitations of the Baltic Sea water quality model, such as a too low DIP pool in deep water and insufficient representation of permanently anoxic sediment pools, have been discussed in Vigouroux et al. (2019), and a CO_2 flux dependent representation of anoxic depth has been implemented here to improve the representation of the sediment pools and fluxes. Too high vertical mixing in the Himmerfjärden Bay hydrodynamic model may further result in too low DIP concentrations in the deep layers, too high bottom temperature leading to too high sediment rates, and possibly too early onset of anoxic conditions. The Chl a conversion from modelled biomass results, with division by a constant (or by season dependent constants), used here is also uncertain. Such methods are also implemented in other Baltic Sea models such as RCO-SCOBI (Eilola et al., 2009) and BALTSEM (Savchuk et al., 2012), and may be used to assess trends and changes in Chl a concentrations. However, the limited availability and time coverage of monitoring data generally does not allow for rigorous validation of any model, and further justifies the use of a consistent relatively simple scalable modelling approach.

These types of uncertainties and data limitations generally make model use and quantification of management effects challenging. Ensemble model studies may be used for more robust results and uncertainty estimations, but are computationally expensive. The aforementioned uncertainties and lack of coastal data for rigorous validation of the Himmerfjärden water quality model do not allow for specific prediction of coastal water quality and ecosystem status. However, the Baltic Sea model validation and general agreement with results from other Baltic Sea models (Meier et al., 2012), along with overall agreement of the present Himmerfjärden case study with other related coastal studies (e.g., Engqvist, 1996; Jones et al., 2018) indicate that the uncertainties do not undermine the model ability to suitably describe the coastal system for the scenario analysis purposes of this study.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we have used a relatively simple modelling approach to investigate management scenario effects on coastal eutrophication indicators under different hydroclimatic conditions in the case of the Baltic Himmerfjärden Bay. Main conclusions from the study can be summarized as follows:

- Hydroclimatic conditions, e.g., expressed in terms of heat flux and river discharges, are essential for the effectiveness of coastal eutrophication mitigation and management.
- The studied water quality components (DIN, DIP and Chl a) are affected differently by land, coastal and sea-based management measures, and a combination of land and sea measures is needed to reach overall good status for all components. Moreover, management control of the resulting coastal DIN/DIP ratio is necessary to avoid both cyanobacteria blooms and increased nitrogen export to the open sea.
- Internal loading of phosphorus can complicate management of coastal eutrophication, but is not the main driver of coastal eutrophication in the Himmerfjärden Bay case.
- Drier–colder conditions imply easier coastal eutrophication mitigation and management towards good ecological status. Wetter–warmer conditions decrease mitigation effects and complicate the management pathways. Hydroclimate is thus an important non-human control on efforts to improve coastal water quality and ecological status.
- Projected climate change for the Baltic region tends towards wetter–warmer conditions, for which achievement of good coastal water quality status will be more difficult. Under such conditions, combined land- and sea-based measures for eutrophication management are needed to achieve good coastal conditions.
- In order to choose specific coastal management measures, however, more specific predictive modelling is needed of each measure and of hydroclimatic and open sea conditions, along with enhanced availability and open accessibility to relevant coastal data.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2020.105360>.

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